

The role of R&D in the effectiveness of renewable energy determinants: A spatial econometric analysis[☆]

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates the effects of renewable energy determinants on various renewable energy resources. The empirical results are based on data from 31 mainly Asia-Pacific countries observed from 2000 to 2018. Different diagnostic tests indicate the existence of spatial effects in the renewable energy model. The spatial Durbin model with the time-period and spatial fixed effects was selected for analysis. Scrutinizing empirical studies suggest a lack of theoretical consensus on how renewable energy determinants work. By examining how R&D affects different renewable energy resources, this study attempts to fill the research gap. In addition, the R&D environment is an important factor in determining the effects of GDP and the development of financial markets and institutions. R&D enhancement reduces the impacts of market expansion on hydropower; however, such effects are incremental for solar, wind, bioenergy, and geothermal energy resources. In an environment with a low level of R&D, financial development has positive effects on hydropower generation and negative impacts on other renewable energy types. However, the expansion of R&D expands reverses such effects gradually. The different results are obtained for different countries at different levels of R&D. Furthermore, trade openness has been a positive factor in the development of hydropower, solar and geothermal energy resources. The results also revealed the negative (positive) impacts of GDP per capita in neighboring countries with a higher (lower) level of R&D on the development of renewable energy of the origin country.

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1. Introduction

World energy-related CO₂ emissions grew at an average rate of 1.8% per year from 1990 to 2018. CO₂ emissions are expected to increase at an average rate of 19.2% by 2050 as compared to 2018 (IEO, 2019). Emissions of greenhouse gases (GHG) will lead to global warming with negative effects on the environment. Therefore, CO₂ is considered to be a global issue. The consideration of the increasing utilization of renewable energy technologies has become widespread. The expansion of renewable energy ensures energy security, reduction of production costs, diversification of energy consumption by reducing dependency on using fossil fuels in production. Also, the availability of renewable energy accelerates international trade by reducing production costs, providing higher production efficiency, and expanding production (Qamruzzaman and Jianguo, 2020). Due to the importance of renewable energy development, various studies are conducted on the

determinants of renewable energy utilization. Although the literature is mainly focused on the effects of economic growth, financial development, and trade, no consensus has been reached on the effects.

The relationship between renewable energy consumption and financial development has been considered in various works. A financial system can efficiently direct credit to renewable energy production. Few studies have examined the nexus between financial development and renewable energy. Wu and Broadstock (2015) using data for twenty-two emerging market economies to infer the positive effects of institutional quality and financial development on renewable energy utilization. Drawing on data from 137 countries, Best (2017) found that financial capital harms renewable energy utilization, while such effects are positive for domestic private debt securities and bank credits. Burakov and Freidin (2017) recognized no financial development impacts renewable energy capacity. Kutan et al. (2018) investigated four emerging economies, including South Africa, Brazil, India, and China. They found that stock market development and foreign direct investment stimulate renewable energy use.

Ari and Cergibozan (2017) found that financial development strengthened the use of renewable energy in Turkey in the short run and that renewable energy availability accelerated financial development. Using panel data of the European Union (EU) countries, Anton

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and Nucu (2020) concluded that financial development gave rise to increased renewable energy consumption. Based on their results, capital market development in the new EU member states does not affect renewable energy consumption. Qamruzzaman and Jianguo (2020) confirmed the asymmetric relationships between renewable energy consumption, capital flows, trade openness, and financial development in the long run in all countries. Furthermore, the asymmetric relationship is confirmed, except for lower-income countries in the short run.

The relationship between economic growth and renewable energy has been studied over the past decade. These studies have not reached the same conflicting results. Several studies confirmed the conservation hypothesis, which implies a unilateral causal between economic growth and renewable energy consumption (Tiwari, 2011; and Dong et al., 2018). Some studies provided empirical evidence to approve the growth hypothesis, which emphasizes a unilateral causal from renewable energy consumption toward economic growth, discussing the negative effects of energy conservation policies on the GDP (Bilgili and Ozturk, 2015; Hamit-Haggar, 2016; Balsalobre-Lorente et al., 2018; Adams et al., 2018). Besides, the feedback hypothesis is also verified in other studies that emphasize the bidirectional causality of renewable energy consumption and economic growth (Amri, 2017; Kahia et al., 2017; Al-mulali et al., 2014; Pao and Chen, 2019; Eren et al., 2019). Several works found no causal relationship (Bowden and Payne, 2010; Menegaki, 2011; Dogan, 2015).

Trade openness plays an important role in economic development by expanding the domestic market, export-focused industry, improving bilateral trade relations, and providing access to energy-efficient technologies. Also, economic activity has expanded, and energy consumption in various channels (e.g., meeting the international requirements of surplus production and the import of more machinery and equipment) has increased energy demand (Sadorsky, 2012). Thus, the relationship between open trade availability and energy consumption has been studied in various works (Cole, 2006; Ghani, 2012; Arif et al., 2017). Empirical studies have recently sought to examine the causality between renewable energy and trade openness, among other factors. Arif et al. (2017) investigated the nexus between trade openness and energy consumption in four oil-importing and developing countries, namely India, China, Bangladesh, and Pakistan. They found that there was a unilateral causality from trade openness to energy consumption.

Aïssa et al. (2014) studied the relationship between production, trade, and renewable energy consumption in Africa. The results showed that renewable energy consumption had positive effects on trade in the long term. In the short term, however, there was no causality between renewable energy consumption and trade. Brini et al. (2017) evaluated the relationships between economic growth, oil prices, international trade, and renewable energy consumption in Tunisia. Their findings highlighted bidirectional causality between international trade and renewable energy consumption in the short term. Halicioglu and Ketenci (2018) explored the nexus between non-renewable energy, capital, renewable energy, labor, and international trade. They found evidence of the positive effects of international trade on renewable energy consumption. Mohamed et al. (2019) analyzed the nexus between renewable, terrorism, fossil fuels, trade, and economic growth in France. Their findings indicated bidirectional causality between trade openness and renewable energy consumption.

CO₂ emissions and their role in renewable energy development have been extensively investigated in the empirical literature (Sadorsky, 2009; Aguirre and Ibikunle, 2014). Using a panel of 9 Mediterranean countries, Belaid and Zrelli (2019) found short-term bidirectional causality between CO₂ emissions, renewable electricity consumption, and GDP, and between renewable electricity consumption, GDP, and non-renewable electricity consumption. The results also demonstrated that there was bidirectional causality between CO₂ emissions and non-renewable electricity consumption in the long run. Lin and Zhu (2019) analyzed factors affecting renewable energy technology innovation in Chinese provinces. According to the results, high CO₂ emissions enhance the level of

innovation in renewable energy technology, and research and development (R&D) investments have a positive effect on the level of innovation. However, such effects are negligible for energy prices.

Przychodzen and Przychodzen (2020) addressed the determinants of renewable energy production in transition economies. The results showed that higher economic growth, rising unemployment, the implementation of the Kyoto Protocol, and government debt functioned as the drivers of renewable energy production. Furthermore, increased CO₂ emissions, the implementation of competition policy, and the deterioration of competition in the energy market were found to have limited the production of renewable energy. Also, investing in R&D leads to environmental innovation (Tian et al., 2020; Yu et al., 2020). Consequently, it is expected to help the economy to move toward renewable energy production (Li et al., 2020). R&D is considered to be a determinant of CO₂ emissions (Fei et al., 2014; Alvarez-Herranz et al., 2017; Shahbaz et al., 2018; Yu and Xu, 2019). Due to its effects on greenhouse gas emissions reduction, it can also lead to renewable energy development; however, empirical studies on the effects of R&D on CO₂ emissions have yielded mixed results, with several articles concluding that R&D has a small influence on CO₂ emissions (Zhai and Song, 2013; Cheng et al., 2019; Chen and Lee, 2020). Such an issue requires a more detailed study of how R&D affects renewable energy development; however, few studies have been conducted in this field.

Due to the lack of consensus on the impacts of common variables on renewable energy resources in empirical works and the need to more accurately investigate the effects of new variables (e.g., R&D and CO₂ emissions), several contributions have been provided. First, the present study separately examines factors affecting the components of renewable energy, including hydropower, solar, wind, bioenergy, and geothermal resources, differently from previous empirical studies. This work can address the asymmetries in how the determinants of renewable energy affect its components and reveal the ultimate effects on total renewable energy. Second, the impacts of R&D on the components of renewable energy are emphasized. Thus, in addition to its direct effects, its spillover impacts on economic growth and financial development are studied. Renewable energy projects are inherently expensive and require long-term debt repayment, high start-up costs, and continued investment in R&D (Sonntag-O'Brien and Usher, 2006; Ziaei, 2021) s shows that the financial constraints and uncertainty impose a substantial impact on those high fixed costs projects (Alhassan and Naka, 2020). Therefore, the development of the renewable energy sector seems to be influenced by the level of R&D. The hypothesis has been studied in this work. Apart from the possibility of a more detailed study on the effects of R&D on the development of various renewable energy components, such a study could be a step toward bridging the gap in the empirical literature on the lack of consensus on the impacts of economic growth and financial development on energy development. Finally, using spatial econometric models, an attempt has been made to investigate the spillover effects of renewable energy determinants in neighboring countries on the development of renewable energy in the origin country. The non-consideration of such impacts would lead to biased estimates. Thus, accounting for the spatial effects is the last contribution of the present work.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows: Section two describes the methodology and data; Section three provides the empirical results, and Section four concludes the work and provides policy implications.

2. Methodology and data

2.1. Empirical model

The present study employs spatial econometric models to investigate the effects of renewable energy determinants. Therefore, the impacts of independent variables or spillover effects on renewable energy in neighboring countries can be also analyzed. To determine the spatial dependence between observations, different models are

estimated. According to Anselin et al. (2008), a spatial panel data model can follow a spatially autoregressive in error terms or include a lagged dependent variable. The spatial lag model is formulated as:

$$y_{it} = \lambda \sum_{j=1}^N w_{ij} y_{jt} + \varphi + x_{it} \beta + c_i(\text{optional}) + \alpha_t(\text{optional}) + v_{it} \quad (1)$$

where x_{it} denotes a $1 \times K$ vector of independent variables for cross-sectional units $i = 1, \dots, N$ at periods $t = 1, \dots, T$, β is a $K \times 1$ vector of parameters, y_{it} is the dependent variable. Spatial-specific effects assign for space-specific variables, while time-specific effects assign for time-specific effects (Baltagi, 2005). c_i shows a spatial-specific effect, and α_t stands for a time-period specific effect. Also, $\sum w_{ij} y_{jt}$ is the interaction effect of the dependent variables y_{jt} in neighboring units on the dependent variable y_{it} in the specific unit, λ is the parameter of these effects, w_{ij} is element i, j of a $N \times N$ spatial weights matrix w , and v_{it} is a random error term, which is assumed to be independently distributed.

The spatial lag model can be generalized. In the spatial error model introduced below, the error term of unit i , u_{it} , depends on the error terms of neighboring units j , u_{jt} , an idiosyncratic component, v_{it} , and the spatial weights matrix W as.

$$y_{it} = \lambda \sum_{j=1}^N w_{ij} y_{jt} + \varphi + x_{it} \beta + c_i(\text{optional}) + \alpha_t(\text{optional}) + u_{it} \quad (2)$$

$$u_{it} = \rho \sum_{j=1}^N w_{ij} u_{jt} + v_{it}$$

The spatial Durbin model is a generalization of the model, which combines spatially lagged independent variables with the spatial lag model as (LeSage and Pace, 2009, Ch. 6):

$$y_{it} = \lambda \sum_{j=1}^N w_{ij} y_{jt} + \varphi + x_{it} \beta + \sum_{j=1}^N w_{ij} x_{jt} \theta + c_i(\text{optional}) + \alpha_t(\text{optional}) + v_{it} \quad (3)$$

where θ is a $K \times 1$ vector of parameters. As mentioned, many different factors impact renewable energy production. In line with Zhao et al. (2020), the explanatory variables are some of the drivers of renewable energy in literature. The logarithm of renewable energy capacity per capita is considered to be a function of the logarithm of GDP per capita ($\ln GDP$), the logarithm of trade openness ($\ln OPE$), the logarithm of R&D index ($\ln RD$), and the logarithm of financial development ($\ln FD$). Also, the effects of the determinants on renewable energy components, including hydropower, solar, wind, bioenergy, and geothermal energy, have been studied in different models.

Different models have been estimated to investigate the effects of model variables on renewable energy. First, to evaluate the contributions of GDP per capita and R&D investments, the following models are estimated:

$$\ln RENEW_{it} = \beta_1 + \beta_2 \ln GDP_{it} + \beta_3 \ln OPE_{it} + \beta_4 \ln RD_{it} + c_i(\text{optional}) + \alpha_t(\text{optional}) + v_{it} \quad (4)$$

$$\ln RENEW_{it} = \beta_1 + \beta_2 \ln GDP_{it} + \beta_3 \ln OPE_{it} + \beta_4 \ln RD_{it} + \beta_5 (\ln RD_{it} \times \ln GDP_{it}) + c_i(\text{optional}) + \alpha_t(\text{optional}) + v_{it} \quad (5)$$

where $(\ln RD_{it} \times \ln GDP_{it})$ represents the R&D and economic growth interactive term. The impact of GDP per capita on renewable energy capacity is obtained as:

$$\frac{d(\ln RENEW_{it})}{d(\ln GDP_{it})} = \beta_2 + \beta_5 \ln RD_{it} \quad (6)$$

Theoretically, financial development leads to economic growth and technological advancement, enhancing energy consumption. This

implies that the improved financial sector leads to more affordable access to credit for the purchase of new machinery and equipment that require more energy to consume (Sadorsky, 2010, 2011; Acheampong, 2019). Also, financial development through technology development and coupled with environmental incentive programs can afford firms to adopt environmentally efficient technologies (Tamazian and Rao, 2010; Zagorchev et al., 2011). Such effects require the availability of technological bases in countries so it seems that in countries with higher levels of R&D, the effects of financial development on high-tech renewable energy are greater. To investigate the joint influences of R&D and financial development on renewable energy, Eqs. (7) and (8) incorporate the interaction term of R&D and financial development ($\ln RD_{it} \times \ln FD_{it}$):

$$\ln RENEW_{it} = \beta_1 + \beta_2 \ln GDP_{it} + \beta_3 \ln OPE_{it} + \beta_4 \ln RD_{it} + \beta_5 \ln FD_{it} + c_i(\text{optional}) + \alpha_t(\text{optional}) + v_{it} \quad (7)$$

$$\ln RENEW_{it} = \beta_1 + \beta_2 \ln GDP_{it} + \beta_3 \ln OPE_{it} + \beta_4 \ln RD_{it} + \beta_5 \ln FD_{it} + \beta_6 (\ln RD_{it} \times \ln FD_{it}) + c_i(\text{optional}) + \alpha_t(\text{optional}) + v_{it} \quad (8)$$

The effect of financial development on renewable energy capacity in Eq. (8) is obtained as:

$$\frac{d(\ln RENEW_{it})}{d(\ln FD_{it})} = \beta_5 + \beta_6 \ln RD_{it} \quad (9)$$

At a negative β_5 and β_6 in eqs. 6 and 9, an increase in R&D would reduce the impacts of GDP per capita and financial development on renewable energy capacity, and vice versa.

2.2. Data

This study uses data from 31 mainly Asia-Pacific countries¹ during 2000–2018 to evaluate the factors affecting the development of renewable energy. Fig. 1 shows renewable energy capacity per capita in these countries. All variables are logarithmic; therefore, the estimated coefficients are elasticity. Since the values of dependent variables are zero in some years, their logarithmic values are added to one and incorporated in the models. Table 1 shows a summary of the constructed variables. Also, Table 2 summarizes the statistics of the data.

3. Results and findings

To begin model estimation, it is required to select the optimal models by using a series of hypothesis tests. In this study, six different models were estimated for each renewable energy variable. Estimated models calculated two components of financial development (the development of financial markets and the financial institutions) in eqs. 4 to 7. Since it is not possible to provide the selection test statistics of all non-nested models, only the tests selected for the total renewable energy variable are presented in Tables 3 and 4.

First, the possibility of the presence of time-period and spatial effects should be examined using the Likelihood Ratio (LR) test, where the null hypothesis of the LR test emphasizes the existence of simultaneous time-period and spatial fixed effects, while the alternative hypothesis is the existence of either spatial fixed effects or time-period fixed effects. For this purpose, in the bottom row of each model in Table 3, the LR test statistics are presented. Based on the test results, the test statistic is significant for all models at a significance level of 1%, and the null

¹ Including Armenia, Australia, Azerbaijan, Bangladesh, Brunei, Darussalam, Cambodia, China, Georgia, India, Indonesia, Iran, Japan, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyz Republic, Malaysia, Mongolia, Myanmar, Nepal, New Zealand, Pakistan, Philippines, Russian Federation, Singapore, Sri Lanka, Tajikistan, Thailand, Turkey, Turkmenistan, Uzbekistan, Vietnam, Korea.

Fig. 1. Renewable energy capacity per capita (MW).

hypothesis is not rejected. Therefore, time-period and spatial fixed effects are modeled simultaneously.

In the next step, the possibility of the presence of spatial interaction effects in the model is examined. This is performed using the hypothesis test to check the possibility of the presence of the spatial error or the spatial lag in the model. For this purpose, using a Lagrange Multiplier (LM) test with a chi-squared distribution, the presence of a spatial error autoregressive and spatially-lagged dependent variable in the model is investigated. The test is performed using the residuals of a non-spatial model. If the alternative hypotheses are not rejected, the existence of the spatial lagged or the spatial error in the model is proved,

Table 1
Variables source.

Variable	Variable constructed	Source
$\ln RENEW_{it}$	$\ln RENEW_{it} = \log(1 + RENEW_{it})$ $RENEW_{it}$ = Renewable Energy per capita	SDG
$\ln HYD_{it}$	$\ln HYD_{it} = \log(1 + HYD_{it})$ HYD_{it} = Hydropower Energy per capita	SDG
$\ln SOL_{it}$	$\ln SOL_{it} = \log(1 + SOL_{it})$ SOL_{it} = Solar Energy per capita	SDG
$\ln WIN_{it}$	$\ln WIN_{it} = \log(1 + WIN_{it})$ WIN_{it} = Wind Energy per capita	SDG
$\ln BIO_{it}$	$\ln BIO_{it} = \log(1 + BIO_{it})$ BIO_{it} = Bioenergy Energy per capita	SDG
$\ln GEO_{it}$	$\ln GEO_{it} = \log(1 + GEO_{it})$ GEO_{it} = Geothermal Energy per capita	SDG
$\ln GDPP_{it}$	$\ln GDPP_{it} = \log(GDPP_{it})$ $GDPP_{it}$ = GDP per capita in 2010 prices\$ in the country i in period t	WDI
$\ln OPE_{it}$	$\ln OPE_{it} = \log(OPE_{it})$ OPE_{it} = Trade Openness (total exports and imports divided by GDP)	WDI
$\ln RD_{it}$	$\ln RD_{it} = \log(RD_{it})$ RD_{it} = the number of Scientific and technical journal articles per capita	WDI
$\ln FI_{it}$	$\ln FI_{it} = \log(100 * FI_{it})$ FI_{it} = the Development of Financial Institution	IMF
$\ln FM_{it}$	$\ln FM_{it} = \log(100 * FM_{it})$ FM_{it} = the Development of Financial Market	IMF

WDI: World Development Indicator; <https://datacatalog.worldbank.org/dataset/world-development-indicators>.

SDG: The Asia-Pacific SDG Gateway; <https://data.unescap.org/>

IMF: International Monetary Fund; <https://data.imf.org/>

rejecting the non-spatial model. Considering the existence of the time-period and spatial fixed effects in the model, the LM test statistics of this model are evaluated on the right side of Table 3. The results suggest the significance of the LM test statistics. The rejection of the null hypothesis confirms the existence of spatial interaction effects in the model. Therefore, assuming the presence of the spatial lag or the spatial error in the model, the steps of selecting the optimal model are continued. It should be noted that the values in parentheses in all tables show the estimated p -values.

In the next test, using Hausman test statistics, the probability of choosing a random-effects model rather than a fixed-effects model is analyzed. The alternative hypothesis in this test emphasizes the existence of a random-effects model. The results of the Hausman test for both the spatial Durbin and the spatial lag models (Table 4) are significant at a level of 1%. Therefore, the existence of random effects in the model is rejected.

Finally, two separate hypotheses are considered as $H_0 : \theta = 0$ and $H_0 : \theta + \lambda\beta = 0$ for Eq. (3). If the first assumption holds, the spatial Durbin model converts into a spatial lagged model. Also, if the latter is the case, the spatial Durbin model simplifies into a spatial error model (Burrige, 1980). The confirmation of the spatial Durbin model implies the existence of the spatial lagged independent variable, for which the LR test or Wald test can be used. The test results for the random- and fixed-effects models are presented in Table 4. The LR or Wald test is statistically significant for all models at a level of 1%, suggesting strong

Table 2
Variable statistics in 2000–2018.

Variable	Mean	Median	Maximum	Minimum	Std. Dev.	Observations
$\ln RENEW_{it}$	4.31	4.29	7.37	0	1.77	589
$\ln HYD_{it}$	4	4.14	7.21	0	1.94	589
$\ln SOL_{it}$	0.66	0.04	6.12	0	1.24	589
$\ln WIN_{it}$	0.82	0.02	5.45	0	1.37	589
$\ln BIO_{it}$	1.06	0.45	4.12	0	1.29	589
$\ln GEO_{it}$	0.44	0	5.33	0	1.09	589
$\ln GDPP_{it}$	8.3	8.16	10.99	5.84	1.39	589
$\ln OPE_{it}$	4.16	4.15	6.08	-1.79	0.92	589
$\ln RD_{it}$	3.9	3.8	7.72	-1.47	2.16	589
$\ln FI_{it}$	3.63	3.6	4.57	2.14	0.48	589
$\ln FM_{it}$	2.7	3.25	4.53	0.02	1.48	589

Table 3
Spatial lag or spatial error in the time-period and spatial fixed effect model.

		Pooled OLS		Spatial fixed effects		Time-period fixed effects		Time-period and spatial fixed effects	
Model F1	LM spatial lag	3.849	(0.05)	2.876	(0.09)	14.604	(0.000)	19.389	(0.000)
	LM spatial error	4.749	(0.029)	4.766	(0.029)	4.177	(0.041)	19.952	(0.000)
	LR-test			1736.262	(0.000)	47.493	(0.000)		
Model F2	LM spatial lag	4.237	(0.04)	3.096	(0.078)	14.774	(0.000)	20.503	(0.000)
	LM spatial error	4.413	(0.036)	3.547	(0.06)	4.276	(0.039)	23.114	(0.000)
	LR-test			1736.681	(0.000)	47.382	(0.000)		
Model F3	LM spatial lag	1.146	(0.284)	3.42	(0.064)	15.893	(0.000)	18.593	(0.000)
	LM spatial error	6.57	(0.01)	4.311	(0.038)	5.352	(0.021)	18.831	(0.000)
	LR-test			1711.933	(0.000)	44.27	(0.001)		
Model F4	LM spatial lag	3.594	(0.058)	5.381	(0.02)	18.296	(0.000)	14.358	(0.000)
	LM spatial error	9.854	(0.002)	1.858	(0.173)	8.818	(0.003)	11.193	(0.001)
	LR-test			1768.47	(0.000)	53.942	(0.000)		
Model F5	LM spatial lag	2.134	(0.144)	3.343	(0.067)	20.652	(0.000)	21.414	(0.000)
	LM spatial error	11.235	(0.001)	4.862	(0.027)	9.757	(0.002)	25.6	(0.000)
	LR-test			1709.772	(0.000)	47.669	(0.000)		
Model F6	LM spatial lag	3.382	(0.066)	4.833	(0.028)	17.16	(0.000)	18.605	(0.000)
	LM spatial error	8.586	(0.003)	6.171	(0.013)	7.656	(0.006)	24.529	(0.000)
	LR-test			1787.4	(0.000)	61.624	(0.000)		

Source: Authors' estimations.

observations of the existence of the spatial lagged independent variables in the models. Thus, the spatial Durbin model with the time-period and spatial fixed effects is selected as the optimal model. The estimation results of different models for the renewable energy components are presented in Tables 5-10.

Table 5 provides the estimation results of the hydropower renewable energy model. According to the results, an increase in GDP per capita significantly increases hydropower energy by nearly 0.6%. The effect of the variable in Model A2 based on the interaction terms of the R&D index and GDP per capita is obtained as:

$$\frac{d(\ln HYD_{it})}{d(\ln GDPP_{it})} = 0.686 - 0.097 \ln RD_{it}$$

According to this equation, a rise in GDP per capita as an indicator of market scale raises hydropower energy production; however, R&D enhancement reduces the positive. This suggests that technological

growth decreases the production of traditional renewable energy resources such as hydropower. The maximum logarithmic value of R&D is 7.72. Thus, the final effects of GDP per capita are positive, even in countries with the highest level of technology, but lower than that in other countries.

Trade openness has a significant, positive effect on hydropower energy at a level of 1%. A rise in trade openness increases hydropower energy by approximately 0.14%. The effect of financial institution development is significant in Model A3 and Model A5, while such positive effects of financial market development are observed only after the entry of the interaction variables of financial development and R&D in Model A6. The impacts of developing financial markets and institutions on hydropower energy production in Models A6 and A5 models are calculated as:

$$\frac{d(\ln HYD_{it})}{d(\ln FI_{it})} = 0.813 - 0.139 \ln RD_{it}$$

Table 4
Spatial Durbin model and Hausman test results.

Random effects estimator						
	Model F1	Model F2	Model F3	Model F4	Model F5	Model F6
Wald test: spatial Durbin model against spatial lag model	51.99 (0.000)	197.201 (0.000)	58.073 (0.000)	74.427 (0.000)	164.756 (0.000)	169.059 (0.000)
Wald test: spatial Durbin model against spatial error model	17.898 (0.000)	124.292 (0.000)	23.289 (0.000)	50.336 (0.000)	100.233 (0.000)	121.4 (0.000)
LR test: spatial Durbin model against spatial lag model	43.882 (0.000)	135.165 (0.000)	49.46 (0.000)	62.481 (0.000)	96.012 (0.000)	126.508 (0.000)
LR test: spatial Durbin model against spatial error model	36.86 (0.000)	107.966 (0.000)	42.587 (0.000)	60.637 (0.000)	74.992 (0.000)	107.953 (0.000)
Fixed effects estimator						
Wald test: spatial Durbin model against spatial lag model	144.194 (0.000)	273.689 (0.000)	150.961 (0.000)	144.908 (0.000)	243.975 (0.000)	257.423 (0.000)
Wald test: spatial Durbin model against spatial error model	84.929 (0.000)	205.949 (0.000)	91.176 (0.000)	113.063 (0.000)	181.703 (0.000)	211.184 (0.000)
LR test: spatial Durbin model against spatial lag model	90.607 (0.000)	213.319 (0.000)	99.374 (0.000)	110.424 (0.000)	187.127 (0.000)	198.224 (0.000)
LR test: spatial Durbin model against spatial error model	69.225 (0.000)	170.661 (0.000)	77.697 (0.000)	96.668 (0.000)	151.76 (0.000)	166.788 (0.000)
Hausman test						
Hausman test-statistic: the spatial lag model	2605.603 (0.000)	938.3194 (0.000)	3724.84 (0.000)	2528.438 (0.000)	854.3867 (0.000)	1036.513 (0.000)
Hausman test-statistic: the spatial Durbin model	191.9473 (0.000)	240.0573 (0.000)	273.6532 (0.000)	94.07503 (0.000)	741.2811 (0.000)	211.0349 (0.000)

Source: Authors' estimations.

Table 5
Hydropower energy estimates.

	Model A1	Model A2	Model A3	Model A4	Model A5	Model A6
<i>lnGDPP</i>	0.664 (0.000)	0.686 (0.000)	0.562 (0.000)	0.669 (0.000)	0.423 (0.000)	0.549 (0.000)
<i>lnOPE</i>	0.146 (0.000)	0.126 (0.000)	0.15 (0.000)	0.124 (0.000)	0.149 (0.000)	0.096 (0.000)
<i>lnRD</i>	0.293 (0.000)	1.075 (0.000)	0.276 (0.000)	0.27 (0.000)	0.785 (0.000)	0.502 (0.000)
<i>lnRD × lnGDPP</i>		-0.097 (0.000)				
<i>lnFI</i>			0.396 (0.000)		0.813 (0.000)	
<i>lnFM</i>				0.076 (0.149)		0.303 (0.000)
<i>lnRD × lnFI</i>					-0.149 (0.000)	
<i>lnRD × lnFM</i>						-0.081 (0.000)
<i>W × lnGDPP</i>	0.49 (0.000)	0.837 (0.000)	0.628 (0.000)	0.599 (0.000)	0.533 (0.001)	0.722 (0.000)
<i>W × lnOPE</i>	0.022 (0.828)	0.058 (0.538)	0.056 (0.586)	0.035 (0.732)	0.083 (0.397)	0.079 (0.411)
<i>W × lnRD</i>	0.004 (0.949)	1.847 (0.000)	0.04 (0.512)	-0.011 (0.853)	1.758 (0.000)	0.333 (0.000)
<i>W × lnRD × lnGDPP</i>		-0.219 (0.000)				
<i>W × lnFI</i>			-0.231 (0.392)		1.149 (0.002)	
<i>W × lnFM</i>				-0.494 (0.000)		-0.118 (0.435)
<i>W × lnRD × lnFI</i>					-0.456 (0.000)	
<i>W × lnRD × lnFM</i>						-0.134 (0.000)
<i>W × lnHYD</i>	0.152 (0.005)	0.032 (0.555)	0.162 (0.003)	0.169 (0.002)	0.063 (0.252)	0.075 (0.173)

Source: Authors' estimations.

$$\frac{d(\ln HYD_{it})}{d(\ln FM_{it})} = 0.303 - 0.089 \ln RD_{it}$$

Hence, the development of markets and financial institutions by expanding credits for the production sector allows for enhancing hydropower energy production. However, an increase in the level of technology in a country diminishes such positive effects and the transfer of credit resources for the production of this type of renewable energy. A maximum R&D value of 7.72 suggests that the development of financial markets and financial institutions has a negative final impact on hydropower energy production in countries with a higher level of R&D. At the same time, financial development in such countries decreases the credibility of hydropower energy.

The R&D variable in Model A1 shows a significant, positive influence on hydropower energy. These impacts are calculated in other models as:

$$\frac{d(\ln HYD_{it})}{d(\ln RD_{it})} = 1.075 - 0.097 \ln GDPP_{it}$$

$$\frac{d(\ln HYD_{it})}{d(\ln RD_{it})} = 0.785 - 0.149 \ln FI_{it}$$

$$\frac{d(\ln HYD_{it})}{d(\ln RD_{it})} = 0.502 - 0.081 \ln FM_{it}$$

The maximum logarithmic GDP per capita, financial institution development, and financial market development values are 10.98, 4.57, and 4.53, respectively. The insertion of these values in the proposed equations demonstrates that the final effect of the R&D index on hydropower renewable energy is significant and positive; however, a rise in financial development and market scale diminishes such positive

impacts. For countries with substantially high GDP per capita, these impacts can even be slightly negative.

The effects of solar energy's determinants estimated in Table 6 suggest relatively inverse effects as compared to hydropower energy in Table 5. An increase of 1% in GDP per capita resulted in a significant decrease of 1.06% in solar energy in Model B1 (Table 6). However, by incorporating the interaction term into Model B2, the impact of an increase of 1% in GDP per cap on solar energy is obtained as:

$$\frac{d(\ln SOL_{it})}{d(\ln GDPP_{it})} = -1.178 + 0.265 \ln RD_{it}$$

Thus, increased R&D increases the positive effects of GDP per capita on solar energy. The minimum and maximum logarithmic R&D values were found to be -1.46 and 7.71, respectively. The insertion of these two values in the above equation reveals that the final effect of GDP per capita on solar energy production is negative in countries with low R&D levels. However, in countries with high levels of R&D, the final effects are positive. According to the results, a rise of 1% in trade openness leads to an increase of nearly 0.1% in solar energy production in Models B2 and B5. This is in line with Table 5. The direct impacts of the development of financial markets and financial institutions on solar energy production in Models B3 and B4 are insignificant. However, once the interaction term of R&D and financial development is introduced to Models B5 and B6, the effects of the development of financial institutions and financial markets on the generation of solar energy are obtained as:

$$\frac{d(\ln SOL_{it})}{d(\ln FI_{it})} = -2.151 + 0.486 \ln RD_{it}$$

Table 6
Solar energy estimates.

	Model B1	Model B2	Model B3	Model B4	Model B5	Model B6
<i>lnGDPP</i>	-1.058 (0.000)	-1.178 (0.000)	-0.848 (0.000)	-0.979 (0.000)	-0.526 (0.006)	-0.732 (0.000)
<i>lnOPE</i>	0.029 (0.578)	0.146 (0.003)	0.034 (0.513)	-0.047 (0.379)	0.081 (0.09)	0.03 (0.564)
<i>lnRD</i>	-0.134 (0.045)	-2.221 (0.000)	-0.085 (0.209)	-0.207 (0.002)	-1.727 (0.000)	-0.829 (0.000)
<i>lnRD × lnGDPP</i>		0.265 (0.000)				
<i>lnFI</i>			-0.62 (0.003)		-2.151 (0.000)	
<i>lnFM</i>				0.105 (0.299)		-0.567 (0.000)
<i>lnRD × lnFI</i>					0.486 (0.000)	
<i>lnRD × lnFM</i>						0.226 (0.000)
<i>W × lnGDPP</i>	1.016 (0.000)	1.262 (0.000)	0.492 (0.119)	1.301 (0.000)	0.343 (0.252)	1.329 (0.000)
<i>W × lnOPE</i>	0.311 (0.115)	0.323 (0.072)	0.199 (0.312)	0.324 (0.098)	0.159 (0.392)	0.444 (0.017)
<i>W × lnRD</i>	0.221 (0.053)	1.603 (0.000)	0.117 (0.318)	0.179 (0.109)	1.151 (0.041)	0.724 (0.000)
<i>W × lnRD × lnGDPP</i>		-0.16 (0.002)				
<i>W × lnFI</i>			1.334 (0.01)		2.572 (0.000)	
<i>W × lnFM</i>				-1.42 (0.000)		-0.798 (0.006)
<i>W × lnRD × lnFI</i>					-0.255 (0.085)	
<i>W × lnRD × lnFM</i>						-0.191 (0.000)
<i>W × lnSOL</i>	-0.337 (0.000)	-0.158 (0.006)	-0.361 (0.000)	-0.294 (0.000)	-0.309 (0.000)	-0.257 (0.000)

Source: Authors' estimations.

$$\frac{d(\ln SOL_{it})}{d(\ln FM_{it})} = -0.567 + 0.226 \ln RD_{it}$$

Based on the minimum and maximum logarithmic R&D values in the equations, it can be said that R&D has a negative impact on solar energy production countries with low R&D levels, while it has a positive influence on solar energy production in high-tech. Thus, the growth of R&D in countries leads to the movement of financial credits toward producing solar energy. Such movements are reversed in low-R&D countries.

R&D enhancement has an insignificant, negative impact on solar energy in models without the interaction term (Table 6). However, as the interaction terms were included in Models B2, B5, and B6, such effects are calculated as:

$$\frac{d(\ln SOL_{it})}{d(\ln RD_{it})} = -2.221 + 0.265 \ln GDP_{it}$$

$$\frac{d(\ln SOL_{it})}{d(\ln RD_{it})} = -1.727 + 0.486 \ln FI_{it}$$

$$\frac{d(\ln SOL_{it})}{d(\ln RD_{it})} = -0.829 + 0.226 \ln FM_{it}$$

The minimum logarithmic GDP per capita, financial market development, and financial institution development values are 5.83, 2.13, and 0.024, respectively. Also, the maximum corresponding values are 10.98, 4.57, and 4.53, respectively. The insertion of these values in the above equation reveals that an increase in the logarithmic R&D value has a negative impact on solar energy production in countries with low levels of GDP per capita and financial development, while such

effects are positive in countries with higher GDP per capita and financial development.

Table 7 represents the effects of wind energy determinants. The positive and negative signs of the coefficients are similar to those of solar energy production, except that the coefficients are significantly smaller. The effects of the trade openness on wind energy production are significant, negative only in Models C1, C3 and C4. The development of financial markets and financial institutions in Model C3 and Model C4 has a significant, positive impact on wind energy production; however, once the interaction term is included in Model C5 and Model C6, such effects are obtained as:

$$\frac{d(\ln WIN_{it})}{d(\ln FI_{it})} = -1.431 + 0.581 \ln RD_{it}$$

$$\frac{d(\ln WIN_{it})}{d(\ln FM_{it})} = -0.482 + 0.24 \ln RD_{it}$$

These results are very similar to those of solar energy; R&D enhancement reverses the negative effects of the development of financial markets and financial institutions on wind energy production. These effects are positive in countries with a high R&D level. Also, the interaction term coefficients of R&D and GDP per capita in Model C2 imply that GDP per capita has a positive impact on wind energy production in countries with a high level of R&D and poses a negative influence in countries with low R&D levels. The R&D variable has a significant effect on wind energy production only when the interaction term is included in the model. The effect of the logarithmic R&D value on wind energy production per capita in models C2, C3, C4 are:

Table 7
Wind energy estimates.

	Model C1	Model C2	Model C3	Model C4	Model C5	Model C6
<i>lnGDP</i>	0.005 (0.978)	-0.078 (0.658)	-0.082 (0.682)	0.017 (0.93)	0.336 (0.078)	0.318 (0.091)
<i>lnOPE</i>	-0.103 (0.052)	0.028 (0.574)	-0.099 (0.063)	-0.16 (0.003)	-0.041 (0.406)	-0.08 (0.118)
<i>lnRD</i>	-0.037 (0.585)	-2.18 (0.000)	-0.05 (0.469)	-0.094 (0.164)	-2.012 (0.000)	-0.759 (0.000)
<i>lnRD × lnGDP</i>		0.272 (0.000)				
<i>lnFI</i>			0.375 (0.079)		-1.431 (0.000)	
<i>lnFM</i>				0.234 (0.021)		-0.482 (0.000)
<i>lnRD × lnFI</i>					0.581 (0.000)	
<i>lnRD × lnFM</i>						0.24 (0.000)
<i>W × lnGDP</i>	0.696 (0.008)	0.78 (0.002)	0.776 (0.016)	0.847 (0.001)	0.687 (0.022)	0.931 (0.000)
<i>W × lnOPE</i>	-0.572 (0.004)	-0.624 (0.001)	-0.548 (0.007)	-0.53 (0.007)	-0.622 (0.001)	-0.522 (0.004)
<i>W × lnRD</i>	0.1 (0.385)	0.423 (0.345)	0.13 (0.275)	0.067 (0.548)	0.478 (0.394)	0 (0.998)
<i>W × lnRD × lnGDP</i>		-0.03 (0.564)				
<i>W × lnFI</i>			-0.086 (0.871)		0.683 (0.323)	
<i>W × lnFM</i>				-1.303 (0.000)		-1.345 (0.000)
<i>W × lnRD × lnFI</i>					-0.066 (0.651)	
<i>W × lnRD × lnFM</i>						0.062 (0.225)
<i>W × lnWIN</i>	-0.101 (0.084)	0.011 (0.846)	-0.098 (0.094)	-0.024 (0.673)	-0.075 (0.195)	-0.137 (0.019)

Source: Authors' estimations.

Table 8
Bioenergy estimates.

	Model D1	Model D2	Model D3	Model D4	Model D5	Model D6
<i>lnGDP</i>	0.177 (0.054)	0.172 (0.052)	0.198 (0.038)	0.253 (0.008)	0.19 (0.048)	0.361 (0.000)
<i>lnOPE</i>	-0.027 (0.28)	-0.005 (0.847)	-0.026 (0.311)	-0.063 (0.013)	-0.012 (0.628)	-0.032 (0.185)
<i>lnRD</i>	0.034 (0.288)	-0.066 (0.553)	0.041 (0.207)	-0.004 (0.907)	-0.045 (0.678)	-0.275 (0.000)
<i>lnRD × lnGDP</i>		0.014 (0.299)				
<i>lnFI</i>			-0.006 (0.955)		-0.121 (0.375)	
<i>lnFM</i>				-0.021 (0.667)		-0.316 (0.000)
<i>lnRD × lnFI</i>					0.026 (0.389)	
<i>lnRD × lnFM</i>						0.099 (0.000)
<i>W × lnGDP</i>	0.175 (0.16)	0.423 (0.001)	0.05 (0.745)	0.359 (0.005)	-0.085 (0.573)	0.344 (0.004)
<i>W × lnOPE</i>	0.183 (0.052)	0.202 (0.026)	0.167 (0.082)	0.161 (0.086)	0.17 (0.069)	0.276 (0.002)
<i>W × lnRD</i>	0.061 (0.262)	1.513 (0.000)	0.044 (0.442)	0.044 (0.406)	1.443 (0.000)	0.603 (0.000)
<i>W × lnRD × lnGDP</i>		-0.173 (0.000)				
<i>W × lnFI</i>			0.323 (0.202)		1.61 (0.000)	
<i>W × lnFM</i>				-0.667 (0.000)		-0.002 (0.987)
<i>W × lnRD × lnFI</i>					-0.372 (0.000)	
<i>W × lnRD × lnFM</i>						-0.213 (0.000)
<i>W × lnBIO</i>	-0.282 (0.000)	-0.164 (0.004)	-0.266 (0.000)	-0.283 (0.000)	-0.227 (0.000)	-0.095 (0.093)

Source: Authors' estimations.

Table 9
Geothermal energy estimates.

	Model E1	Model E2	Model E3	Model E4	Model E5	Model E6
<i>lnGDPP</i>	-0.149 (0.053)	-0.174 (0.019)	-0.122 (0.12)	-0.12 (0.138)	-0.012 (0.875)	-0.069 (0.386)
<i>lnOPE</i>	0.01 (0.649)	0.041 (0.051)	0.017 (0.42)	-0.001 (0.981)	0.03 (0.138)	0.021 (0.332)
<i>lnRD</i>	-0.036 (0.175)	-0.586 (0.000)	-0.017 (0.517)	-0.047 (0.087)	-0.53 (0.000)	-0.196 (0.000)
<i>lnRD × lnGDPP</i>		0.07 (0.000)				
<i>lnFI</i>			0.061 (0.468)		-0.406 (0.000)	
<i>lnFM</i>				-0.023 (0.582)		-0.191 (0.000)
<i>lnRD × lnFI</i>					0.152 (0.000)	
<i>lnRD × lnFM</i>						0.055 (0.000)
<i>W × lnGDPP</i>	-0.098 (0.347)	-0.044 (0.683)	-0.395 (0.002)	-0.044 (0.683)	-0.396 (0.001)	0.01 (0.921)
<i>W × lnOPE</i>	-0.012 (0.876)	-0.025 (0.74)	-0.06 (0.444)	-0.024 (0.761)	-0.082 (0.283)	0.028 (0.724)
<i>W × lnRD</i>	0.102 (0.025)	0.111 (0.55)	0.06 (0.195)	0.097 (0.033)	-0.03 (0.898)	0.383 (0.000)
<i>W × lnRD × lnGDPP</i>		0.002 (0.945)				
<i>W × lnFI</i>			0.896 (0.000)		0.95 (0.001)	
<i>W × lnFM</i>				-0.173 (0.108)		0.16 (0.19)
<i>W × lnRD × lnFI</i>					0.031 (0.611)	
<i>W × lnRD × lnFM</i>						-0.106 (0.000)
<i>W × lnGEO</i>	0.03 (0.606)	0.029 (0.617)	-0.029 (0.611)	0.024 (0.684)	-0.051 (0.373)	0.047 (0.407)

Source: Authors' estimations.

$$\frac{d(\ln WIN_{it})}{d(\ln RD_{it})} = -2.18 + 0.272 \ln GDPP_{it}$$

$$\frac{d(\ln WIN_{it})}{d(\ln RD_{it})} = -2.012 + 0.581 \ln FI_{it}$$

$$\frac{d(\ln WIN_{it})}{d(\ln RD_{it})} = -0.759 + 0.24 \ln FM_{it}$$

These formulations suggest that R&D has almost the same impact on wind energy production as that of solar energy, and the same interpretations can be applied.

Table 8 reports the bioenergy renewable energy estimates. As can be seen, only the coefficients of the logarithmic GDP per capita are positive and significant; a rise of 1% in GDP per capita raises bioenergy energy production by nearly 0.2%. Furthermore, the evaluation of the Model D6 coefficients implies that financial market development has a positive influence on bioenergy energy production in high-R&D countries and a negative impact in countries with a low R&D level. The interaction term coefficient in Model D6 suggests that R&D has positive effects on bioenergy energy production; in countries with a higher level of financial market development, such positive effects are greater.

The examination and comparison of geothermal models in Table 6 to wind energy in Table 7 indicate that the independent variables have almost the same influences on wind energy and geothermal energy, and the same interpretation can be applied to both types of energy.

Finally, Table 10 represents the analysis results of the total renewable energy. It is equal to a total of five renewable energy resources. As hydropower accounts for a large portion of renewable energy

production (nearly 85% on average) across the world, Tables 10 and 5 show very similar results.

Spatial models allow for distinguishing the direct and indirect effects of independent variables on a dependent variable. Direct impact estimation measures the effects of a change in an independent variable on a dependent variable within a particular spatial unit. Apart from estimating indirect effects, it measures the effects of changes in an independent variable of other units on the dependent variable of a particular unit. Table 11 shows the direct and indirect effects of Models A2, B2, C2, D2, E2, and F2 for all renewable energy variables. A comparison of Table 11 to the other estimation results indicates that the direct effects are slightly different from the estimated parameters since indirect effects include feedback impacts resulting from crossing neighboring states and returning to the origin state.

The indirect influences of independent variables in the neighboring countries on dependent variables indicate the significance of such effects for some of the studied variables. The GDP per capita of the neighboring countries has a significant, positive impact on hydropower, wind, solar, and bioenergy energy resources in the origin country. Due to the negative coefficient of the interaction term of GDP per capita and R&D, a rise in R&D within the neighboring countries diminishes such positive effects. Also, the significant, negative influence of the interaction term coefficients of hydropower, solar, and bioenergy energy models imply that GDP per capita of the neighboring countries with a high level of R&D negatively impacted hydropower, solar, and bioenergy energy in the origin country. However, such effects are positive for countries whose neighboring countries have low levels of R&D.

The effects of trade openness of the neighboring countries on total renewable energy are negative and insignificant. Such effects were found to be significant and negative for wind energy and positive for bioenergy.

Table 10
Total renewable energy estimates.

	Model F1	Model F2	Model F3	Model F4	Model F5	Model F6
<i>lnGDPP</i>	0.374 (0.000)	0.363 (0.000)	0.299 (0.005)	0.294 (0.005)	0.167 (0.1)	0.195 (0.044)
<i>lnOPE</i>	0.126 (0.000)	0.134 (0.000)	0.128 (0.000)	0.102 (0.000)	0.142 (0.000)	0.093 (0.000)
<i>lnRD</i>	0.274 (0.000)	0.76 (0.000)	0.262 (0.000)	0.253 (0.000)	0.616 (0.000)	0.387 (0.000)
<i>lnRD × lnGDPP</i>		-0.059 (0.000)				
<i>lnFI</i>			0.297 (0.009)		0.552 (0.000)	
<i>lnFM</i>				0.233 (0.000)		0.35 (0.000)
<i>lnRD × lnFI</i>					-0.103 (0.002)	
<i>lnRD × lnFM</i>						-0.044 (0.002)
<i>W × lnGDPP</i>	1.043 (0.000)	1.521 (0.000)	1.134 (0.000)	1.114 (0.000)	0.954 (0.000)	1.288 (0.000)
<i>W × lnOPE</i>	-0.091 (0.388)	-0.058 (0.545)	-0.067 (0.53)	-0.024 (0.815)	-0.046 (0.639)	0.062 (0.512)
<i>W × lnRD</i>	0.274 (0.000)	2.645 (0.000)	0.298 (0.000)	0.221 (0.000)	2.894 (0.000)	0.811 (0.000)
<i>W × lnRD × lnGDPP</i>		-0.284 (0.000)				
<i>W × lnFI</i>			-0.144 (0.609)		2.105 (0.000)	
<i>W × lnFM</i>				-0.653 (0.000)		0.038 (0.797)
<i>W × lnRD × lnFI</i>					-0.693 (0.000)	
<i>W × lnRD × lnFM</i>						-0.23 (0.000)
<i>W × lnRENEW</i>	-0.358 (0.000)	-0.358 (0.000)	-0.349 (0.000)	-0.259 (0.000)	-0.374 (0.000)	-0.304 (0.000)

Source: Authors' estimations.

Table 11
Marginal variable impacts on renewable energy resources.

	Direct Effects		Indirect Effects		Total Effects	
	Coefficient	p-value	Coefficient	p-value	Coefficient	p-value
Model A2 Hydropower energy						
<i>lnGDPP</i>	0.696	(0.000)	0.881	(0.000)	1.577	(0.000)
<i>lnOPE</i>	0.126	(0.000)	0.063	(0.52)	0.189	(0.076)
<i>lnRD</i>	1.096	(0.000)	1.942	(0.000)	3.038	(0.000)
<i>lnRD × lnGDPP</i>	-0.099	(0.000)	-0.229	(0.000)	-0.328	(0.000)
Model B2 Solar energy						
<i>lnGDPP</i>	-1.229	(0.000)	1.313	(0.000)	0.085	(0.745)
<i>lnOPE</i>	0.135	(0.01)	0.263	(0.116)	0.398	(0.022)
<i>lnRD</i>	-2.293	(0.000)	1.763	(0.000)	-0.53	(0.279)
<i>lnRD × lnGDPP</i>	0.273	(0.000)	-0.183	(0.000)	0.091	(0.12)
Model C2 Wind power energy						
<i>lnGDPP</i>	-0.063	(0.721)	0.781	(0.005)	0.718	(0.021)
<i>lnOPE</i>	0.025	(0.624)	-0.633	(0.002)	-0.608	(0.004)
<i>lnRD</i>	-2.179	(0.000)	0.438	(0.313)	-1.741	(0.003)
<i>lnRD × lnGDPP</i>	0.272	(0.000)	-0.031	(0.538)	0.241	(0.001)
Model D2 Bioenergy						
<i>lnGDPP</i>	0.153	(0.09)	0.357	(0.005)	0.51	(0.001)
<i>lnOPE</i>	-0.012	(0.641)	0.18	(0.048)	0.168	(0.061)
<i>lnRD</i>	-0.125	(0.264)	1.361	(0.000)	1.236	(0.000)
<i>lnRD × lnGDPP</i>	0.021	(0.133)	-0.157	(0.000)	-0.136	(0.000)
Model E2 Geothermal energy						
<i>lnGDPP</i>	-0.174	(0.029)	-0.049	(0.655)	-0.223	(0.099)
<i>lnOPE</i>	0.04	(0.059)	-0.026	(0.752)	0.014	(0.867)
<i>lnRD</i>	-0.581	(0.000)	0.103	(0.603)	-0.478	(0.062)
<i>lnRD × lnGDPP</i>	0.069	(0.000)	0.003	(0.907)	0.072	(0.018)
Model F2 All renewable energies						
<i>lnGDPP</i>	0.255	(0.01)	1.136	(0.000)	1.391	(0.000)
<i>lnOPE</i>	0.141	(0.000)	-0.085	(0.275)	0.056	(0.446)
<i>lnRD</i>	0.575	(0.000)	1.93	(0.000)	2.506	(0.000)
<i>lnRD × lnGDPP</i>	-0.038	(0.012)	-0.214	(0.000)	-0.253	(0.000)

Source: Authors' estimations.

The results demonstrated that the GDP per capita of neighboring countries with a high level of R&D negatively influences the renewable energy production of the origin country. However, such effects are positive when the neighboring countries have low R&D levels. These results are the case with all the renewable energy resources, except for geothermal energy.

4. Conclusions and policy implication

In this study, the development determinants of renewable energy components are investigated. The sample includes data from 31 Asia-Pacific countries during 2000–2018. The results of different tests indicate the existence of spatial effects in the nexus between model variables. Thus, the spatial Durbin model with time-period and spatial fixed effects was selected to investigate the relationships between the variables. The results of the renewable energy component study were different. The effects of research variables on hydropower energy are different from other energy components. Since hydropower accounts for an average of 85% of renewable energy consumption, the effects of independent variables on hydropower energy and total renewable energy are almost the same. Therefore, if empirical studies do not separate the components of renewable energy and consider only the total renewable energy, the results will show the effects of independent variables on hydropower energy and cannot provide a proper approach to other components.

The results reflect the fact that the development of newer renewable energy such as wind, solar, bioenergy, and geothermal energy resources enjoys higher funds in countries with higher levels of R&D. In countries with lower levels of R&D, larger funds are provided to expand hydropower as an older renewable energy resource with a lower-tech level so that financial development in these countries leads to a decrease in the utilization of solar, wind, bioenergy, and geothermal energy. Moreover, the utilization of hydropower is gradually decreasing while the

level of R&D is going up. In this regard, market expansion has resulted in a higher level of GDP which has greater positive effects on hydropower and bioenergy resources in countries with low R&D while also reducing the use of per capita wind, solar, and geothermal resources.

With the expansion of R&D in countries, the market size has fewer positive effects on hydropower energy. Also, the use of wind, solar, and geothermal resources per capita gradually increases, and the final effects change from negative to positive. The results indicated that financing renewable energy by the financial sector is more limited in countries with lower levels of R&D; thus, the mere financial development of countries cannot be a guarantee for the development of renewable energy. Therefore, policies for expanding R&D by countries or policies to ensure the movement of credit resources toward renewable energy in countries with higher levels of R&D should be considered. Trade openness has positive effects on hydropower, solar and geothermal energy resources. Thus, a theoretical analysis of how it positively affects renewable energy can be expanded.

An increase in GDP per capita as a measure of the market size in neighboring countries primarily leads to increased energy demand in these countries and secondly provides a more competitive structure for energy production than in the origin country. Therefore, with increased GDP per capita and, consequently, increased energy demand in a neighboring country, the demand and production of renewable energy in the origin country increase. However, if the neighboring country has a high level of R&D, a major portion of the demand is met within the neighboring country, and the initial positive effects are decreased due to reduced energy demand in the origin country. Concerning geothermal energy, the negative effects seem to be larger than the positive ones in any level of R&D. However, geographical conditions are a very important factor in the production of this particular type of energy and cover 2.67% of renewable energy production in the sample on average.

The nature of renewable energy, especially newer types such as wind, solar, bioenergy, and geothermal energy, requires more external financing and therefore could be highly leveraged. Projects with high leverage lead to low liquidity, higher risks, and lower investments (Hsu et al., 2014; Singh and Faircloth, 2005). According to the research's results, R&D's low levels in countries exacerbate such conditions and consequently reduce the movement of financial resources toward wind, solar, bioenergy, and geothermal energy sources. Thus, governments' economic stimulus policies must provide the ground so that financial resources can flow into these sectors. Developed countries have pledged billions of dollars to help developing countries through adaptation and mitigation policies through funds such as the Green Fund. The results of this study suggest that developed countries should consider changing or targeting their financial resources through providing technological platforms or implementing supportive policies to cover the risk of investing in renewable resources. Such actions can also pave the way for the movement of domestic financial resources toward renewable resources.

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